

ChatGPT as a journalistic writer: Understanding the risks of AI-generated text

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Artificial Intelligence, particularly language models like ChatGPT, is revolutionizing text generation. This study investigates the risks of integrating AI-generated content in journalism. A pipeline scrapes articles from seven newspaper websites, aggregating and summarizing data. Analysis of AI-generated summaries reveals two key risks: subtle biases that challenge journalistic integrity and objectivity, and the absence of clear informational hierarchy. The research examines content nuances, style variations, and potential biases in AI-generated text. Findings provide critical insights into the challenges of using machine-generated content in journalism, contributing to a deeper understanding of AI's implications in creative text generation and offering guidance for responsible integration of these technologies in journalistic practices.

Keywords: AI; Content Analysis; Journalistic Bias; Language Models; LLMs; Writing

1. Introduction

Over the past few months, the emergence of ChatGPT has brought the concept of a new type of AI technology to the attention of the general public, due to its remarkable ability to efficiently generate various forms of text (Bodani et al., 2023). This conversational language model has captured the imaginations of writers, researchers, and enthusiasts, and it is starting to transform the landscape of content creation, serving as the bedrock for integration into various software applications (Hou et al., 2023), ranging from AI assistants (Piñeiro-Martín et al., 2023) to robotics (Zeng et al., 2023), thus opening a plethora of new possibilities. While these technologies offer great promise, they also raise several concerns. To test the implications and bottlenecks of AI-generated text, this study develops a script to scrape the homepages of various newspapers. It then uses Large Language Models (LLMs) to summarize these homepages and provide an overall summary. The resulting AI-generated texts are then subjected to qualitative content analysis.

2. Background

Although ChatGPT has taken the world by storm, it's important to note that conversational AI has been studied for decades. In fact, ChatGPT represents the

culmination of years of research in artificial intelligence and natural language processing (NLP), blending linguistic study with algorithms, mathematics, and statistics. At its core, ChatGPT is a language model—a machine learning tool that “assigns a probability to each possible next word. Language models can also assign a probability to an entire sentence, telling us that the following sequence has a much higher likelihood of appearing in a text” (Jurafsky & Martin, 2024, p. 32).

In the 1980s, early language models could only offer rudimentary predictions for the next word in a sequence (Rosenfeld, 2000). However, with the advancement of Artificial Intelligent, language models trained on vast amounts of text (Mikolov, 2011) emerged. These models successfully encoded linguistic information in the hidden layers of neural networks through a method called self-supervised learning. This technique utilizes the natural structure of data to create training labels. In the field of natural language processing (NLP), self-supervised learning allows models to extract knowledge from text that has not been labeled, eliminating the need for costly and time-consuming manually labeled data.

During training, the model is fed a large text corpus and tasked with predicting the next word in each sentence, allowing it to learn linguistic patterns, rules, and word-concept relationships. This process helps the model develop an internal representation of language.

Starting in 2017, the introduction of a new architecture featuring the ‘attention layer’—developed by Vaswani et al. (2017)—paved the way for large language models based on the Transformer architecture, which quickly became widely adopted. These Large Language Models (LLMs) are pretrained on vast corpora of text, allowing them to calculate the likelihood of each word in a certain language, based on the words that precede it (Jurafsky & Martin, 2024). As the model processes more examples, it refines its understanding of various linguistic structures. The result of this extensive training is the creation of colossal pre-trained language models designed to predict and mimic the linguistic patterns of an entire language (Manning, 2022).

However, as we delve deeper into the realm of AI-generated text, we must acknowledge the responsibilities that come with such power. If ChatGPT is to be considered a writing assistant, both developers and users share responsibility for the content it generates. Developers are responsible for balancing and testing the training data and processes to mitigate bias, among other factors, while users need to be aware—at least from a high-level perspective—of the training processes to avoid expecting complete accuracy or impartiality on certain topics (Jiao et al., 2024). One significant issue that arises is the problem of hallucinations, meaning sentences and answers that are linguistically convincing but factually incorrect (Azamfirei et al., 2023). In

fact, these models are designed to provide users with the most probable and linguistically plausible information. They are linguistically convincing, but they operate based on word likelihood. Therefore, they could potentially be trained on 'impossible language', as discussed by Chomsky and Moro (Chomsky & Moro, 2022): if models were trained on incorrect data, they would still reproduce that data faithfully, even if it contained inaccuracies in language or information. Language models can replicate data effectively, but they lack a true understanding of the content.

In this context, new ethical problems are emerging. If AI-generated texts appear linguistically convincing but may also contain incorrect factual information, it is important to be informed when a text has been written by an AI. Certainly, we should. However, the question remains: can we be certain that a text has been authored by an AI? It appears that the technical answer is no. OpenAI, the now-famous company that released ChatGPT, published an article at the end of January 2023, presenting a classifier¹ capable of detecting texts generated by artificial intelligence for the general public (Kirchner, 2023). They described the training process of this model as a general language model fine-tuned on two different datasets: the first dataset included texts generated by an AI, and the other dataset comprised text written by humans. However, by the end of June, this classifier was withdrawn from release due to its being considered unreliable. The Verge commented on the situation, stating: "It seems that for now, no one, not even the company that helped kickstart the generative AI craze in the first place, has answers on how to deal with it all" (The Verge, July 25, 2023, p. 2). Even the creators of ChatGPT were unable to train a reliable classifier to detect text generated by ChatGPT.

Based on studies trying to sketch an overview of the field, research aimed at enhancing the linguistic credibility of these models is progressing much faster than the research focused on identifying AI-generated text (Naveed et al., 2023). If our objective is to develop a generalist model for detecting AI-generated text, the challenge certainly appears difficult. However, many researchers have recently explored ways to fine-tune models for the detection of specific discourses rather than training a generalist model. Indeed, when the scope of detection is narrowed to specific and well-defined discourses, the linguistic cues become more apparent, leading to improved model performance. For instance, a study by Mitrović et al. (2023), specifically targeted at the identification of ChatGPT-generated text in the context of restaurant reviews, revealed interesting findings. ChatGPT's writing exhibited characteristics such as politeness, a lack of specific details, occasional use of elaborate and unconventional vocabulary, an impersonal tone, and a general absence of emotional expression. Intriguingly, the study also revealed that these models still lack the depth of human language, including the ability to employ irony, metaphors, and other linguistic nuances. In a recent

investigation conducted by Weber-Wulff et al. (2023), the researchers evaluated various tools designed to detect AI-generated text. They analyzed 12 free tools alongside two commercial systems. The results revealed that these detection tools generally lack accuracy and reliability. Furthermore, they showed a tendency to classify text as being written by humans rather than effectively identifying content produced by AI. Additionally, the performance of these tools noticeably degrades when confronted with content obfuscation techniques, such as rephrasing or the use of prompts¹ that encourage the direct prevention of plagiarism.

Given the rapid pace of research aimed at making these models' utterances indistinguishable from those of humans, it can be challenging to keep up with counter-solutions. Another study by Pegoraro et al. (2023) has revealed that the majority of software applications designed to detect AI-generated texts exhibit a reliability of less than 50% (Guo et al., 2023; Ippolito et al., 2020; Ma et al., 2023). Other papers presenting software applications for detecting AI-written text share another common issue prevalent in the field of machine learning: the problem of overfitting, which involves training a model to evaluate data that closely resembles the training set. This issue pertains to the evaluation set being too similar to the training set, thus creating an illusion of high accuracy, sometimes for commercial reasons (Compilatio, 2023; Crossplag.com, 2023; GoWinston.ai, 2023; ZeroGPT, 2023). Various enterprises have published papers regarding the efficacy of their own software with results that are framed in a way that overstate the efficiency of their software. However, the disconcerting result, common to all these studies, is that paraphrasing strongly lowers the accuracy, bringing it below 30%. Relying on human manual editing introduces uncertainty in identifying text written by AI. Overall, these tools frequently misclassify human-authored documents as AI-generated (resulting in false positives) and often fail to recognize AI-generated texts, labeling them as human-written instead (leading to false negatives). Considering the unreliability of detection tools for AI-generated text, it is imperative to prioritize a prevention-oriented approach rather than relying solely on detection. Equally essential is the need to educate educators about this reality. The emphasis should shift towards implementing pedagogical strategies that teach the ethical usage of generative AI tools. This education should include comprehensive discussions about both the advantages and limitations associated with these tools.

Given the unreliability of AI detection software, the impact of AI in the realm of textual production raises a plethora of ethical implications. If AI-written text becomes ubiquitous and we are unable to detect it, numerous implications arise for academic research, education, politics, misinformation, and journalism. While each of these fields deserves specific focus, we have chosen to concentrate solely on the implications and risks of AI-written text in

journalism. The literature on this topic is quite extensive, and in recent years, owing to the emergence of Language Models and the subsequent open-sourcing and democratization process involving open-source models like LLama (Touvron, 2023), Mistral (Jiang, 2023), and other freely usable models, this body of literature has become even more abundant. Consequently, research on the use of Artificial Intelligence applied to journalism has increased over the years. According to a study published by Calvo-Rubio et al. (2021), the largest number of publications related to this topic is concentrated in the United States, where a surge in scientific production on Artificial Intelligence in journalism began around 2015, experiencing remarkable growth over the years, and reaching 61 publications in 2019.

Many scholars have expressed concerns about these issues. Among the diverse voices, an interesting remark is offered by Diakopoulos (2019). His research focuses on journalists and writing professionals who are increasingly relying on computer algorithms to tell their stories, fundamentally changing the creation, dissemination, and reception of news. Diakopoulos contends that although automation has significant implications, journalists are unlikely to face displacement. While their methods and narratives may evolve, the core values that underpin journalism continue to be the primary influence on news reporting. On a similar line of thought, Broussard (2018, p. 11) coined the neologism "Artificial Unintelligence" and argued that artificial intelligence, despite its catchy name, still has a socially constructed nature that replicates existing structural inequalities, including those present in journalism if we depict AI-generated text as writing assistants. Biases are inherently implemented in deep learning algorithms and language models: if biases like racial and gender discrimination are not intentionally eliminated from the system through careful data management and thorough model evaluation, they can persist. She also points out that the term "artificial intelligence" is misleading and that the optimistic perceptions surrounding AI are misguided, based on her own experiences as a software engineer in Silicon Valley (p. 31). Ultimately, her book highlights the significance of prioritizing human-centered design and fostering collaboration between humans and machines to counteract technological arrogance.

3. Method

After briefly examining some of the published research related to this topic to gain a better understanding of the risks associated with AI-generated text and the possibilities offered by Language Models, we now introduce a specifically devised software that integrates the OpenAI API into a Python script. This enabled us to utilize OpenAI models, specifically the same model implemented in ChatGPT as reviewed by Roumeliotis et al. (2023), for text generation.

In particular, we have developed a script that automatically scrapes news from seven different newspapers in seven different languages, translates all the news into English, and then compiles summaries for each newspaper, along with a general summary for the day's news in English. The software utilizes the DaVinci model, which is the same model implemented in ChatGPT.

The key conceptual steps are outlined as follows:

- 1) The software opens the homepages of seven newspapers, each published in a different language: *The New York Times* and *The Guardian* (English), *Le Monde* (French), *El País* (Spanish), *Bild* (German), *Corriere della Sera* (Italian), and *Aftenposten* (Norwegian);
- 2) It then scrapes all the texts from their homepages, automatically translates them into English, stores the text in a Pandas dataframe, and generates a summary for each website;
- 3) Finally, the software compiles an overall summary of all the collected news articles. This means the final result consists of nine newspaper-specific summaries, followed by a general one.

Considering that language models can predict the next sentence based on previous co-text, a similar approach can be applied to questions. Language models can estimate the likelihood of responses to a given question. Thus, by directly implementing a prompt in the Python pipeline³, we can ask the DaVinci model questions about the scraped text and make it perform automatic summarization. In other words, the Python script can access the homepages, scrape the text, feed it into the DaVinci model, ask the model a question (with a prompt) about the text, and then retrieve an AI-generated text as an answer.

In our devised pipeline, we have implemented two distinct prompts. The first prompt is related to the initial step, which involved summarizing the homepage of each website. For both prompts, we instructed the Language Model to assume the role of a journalist preparing a daily report⁴. This instruction prompts the language model to use an appropriate linguistic register when providing us with the answer, specifying that it should impersonate a journalist, following the prompt engineering indication specified by White et al. (2023). In the prompt, we also specified the type of text the language model would encounter ('Read the first page of the newspaper'), enabling it to better understand and hypothesize the characteristics of that text. This is important because web scraping may yield some mistakes or other types of data from HTML scraping. If the language model can anticipate the type of text it will encounter, it can better handle possible unexpected linguistic events. In the same prompt, we asked the language model to translate the content into English and provide a summary.

The second prompt was then given to the DaVinci model, after loading, in a second step, the automatically generated summaries from the newspaper homepage, and it was as follows: “You are a journalist tasked with preparing a daily report. Take a look at all these news: “. . . Give me an overall summary by selecting the most important information from all of them.” After devising such a pipeline, we tested it on the news from Friday, October 13th. As mentioned, the script automatically scraped the news from the homepage of the newspapers, provided us with several different AI-generated summaries, and then a final overall summary, which we will now analyze.

4. Discussion

Before delving into a more nuanced analysis of the texts, we would like to make a few general comments. When AI-powered algorithms are integrated into journalism software, they are often described as tools that can help reduce bias. However, we would like to emphasize here the opposite viewpoint. News is not just raw data, as Gitelman (2013) cleverly pointed out. On the contrary, it is something that has been carefully selected by a journalist, in our case. When using language modeling for summarizing journalistic texts, not only does the writer's political stance on a particular issue come into play, but also their linguistic perspective on those topics. As for the content of the news, as we saw during the first quarter of October 2023, reporting on the Israel and Palestine issue has unsurprisingly involved significant political opinions. The theoretical perspective we will adopt is Critical Discourse Analysis, drawing on Fairclough's (2013) interdisciplinary approach as a means to study discourse. This approach views language as a form of social practice and aims to identify power relations within language. It does so by attempting to establish a connection between discourses and the social practices in which discourses are embedded. We will now delve into the analysis of the automatically generated summaries by examining or commenting specific sections of them.

One significant observation concerns the presence of political biases, which is particularly evident in the context of sensitive topics like the War between Israel and Palestine. Given that our pipeline involves the creation of a two-folded summary, where news is initially gathered from websites and then compiled into an overall summary, any biases present in the initial summaries will also be reflected in the final summary. Consequently, if any bias is detected in the initial summaries, the same bias will be carried over to the overall summary. Instead of providing objective reporting, political stances are thus subtly inherited, leading to unintended implicit biases. Let us look at the following examples:

- (1) “The top news stories include the ongoing conflict between Israel and Hamas, the US families of Hamas attack victims

- telling of ‘total horror’” (Automatic summary from *The Guardian* homepage, October 13th, 2023)
- (2) “In Israel, the government has banned a pro-Palestinian demonstration, UN Secretary-General Antonio Guterres has called for humanitarian access to Gaza, and Israeli Prime Minister Benjamin Netanyahu has declared that the one-week counteroffensive is only the beginning” (Automatic summary from the *Bild* homepage, October 13th, 2023)
 - (3) “Today’s top stories include the ongoing conflict between Israel and Hamas, a stabbing in Beijing at the Israeli embassy . . .” (Automatic summary from *Il Corriere della Sera* homepage, October 13th, 2023)
 - (4) Today’s newspaper reports on the escalating conflict between Israel and Hamas, which has caused thousands of Palestinians to flee northern Gaza in panic . . . The war is inflaming tensions across the Middle East, and the U.S. is trying to broker a way out of Gaza for foreigners and set up Palestinian “safe zones” (Automatic summary from *The New York Times* homepage, October 13th, 2023)
 - (5) Hamas has reported that 70 people were killed in an Israeli air strike while attempting to evacuate. (Automatic summary from the *Aftenposten* homepage, October 13th, 2023)

The AI-generated summary of *The Guardian* homepage underscores that the initial witnesses to the Hamas attacks are identified as ‘US families’ who characterize the attacks as ‘total horror’. The emphasis on the nationality of the witnesses gives it an American perspective, introducing a political aspect by suggesting that the report focuses on American witnesses without mentioning casualties from the other side. In the summary from *Bild*, Israeli Prime Minister Netanyahu is quoted as stating that the one-week counteroffensive against Palestine is ‘just the beginning’. This strongly worded choice implies a negative sentiment and reflects the anger of the Israeli people toward Hamas. The language used is firmly positioned, so that, if the linguistic data in the summary is biased, the overall summary, compiled by selecting information for the seven intermediate summaries, may also adopt this tone. In the Italian newspaper *Il Corriere della Sera*, a murder that occurred at the Israeli embassy is reported, emphasizing that Hamas sympathizers are carrying out terror attacks outside of the Middle East. However, once again, the summary avoids mentioning casualties from the other side of the conflict. Needless to say, *The New York Times* presents a US-centric perspective, initially stating that Israeli attacks on northern Gaza are compelling Palestinians to ‘flee’, a verb that suggests many victims were forced to relocate. However, the violence originated from the

Hamas attack, and the subsequent Israeli response caused not only relocations but also numerous casualties. Semantics here are clearly intertwined with a political stance. The selection of specific words subtly frames the event, embedding a viewpoint that can be difficult to challenge directly without appearing biased oneself. This aligns with Leonard's (2024, p. 161) observation regarding effective ideological rhetoric, noting that it can be "so oratorically persuasive it is difficult to conceptualise a response that does not sound discompassionate," essentially shaping the narrative in a way that preempts or delegitimizes alternative perspectives. Furthermore, in another instance *The New York Times* underscores the role of the US in promoting peace by mentioning the US government's efforts to broker a way out of Gaza and establish 'safe zones'. As some intellectuals have pointed out, both in Italy and globally, the situation is highly complex and multifaceted. Some vehemently condemn Hamas as a terrorist organization, while others attribute the responsibility for these tensions to the United States (Chomsky & Vltchek, 2017), a conflict that has persisted for seven decades. Again, the terms selected by the AI to describe these actions and situations, such as 'flee', or the very concept of 'safe zones' in this context, are not merely neutral descriptors. They serve as examples of how definitions and lexical choices fulfill a 'crucial role' in framing reality, inevitably reflecting 'ideological implications' and revealing 'cognitive attitudes and power roles' that are either present in the source texts or embedded within the AI's training and operational logic (Polese, 2017, p. 157). *Aftenposten* highlights a different angle on the Hamas issue, pointing out that Hamas reported 70 casualties resulting from Israeli actions during an evacuation attempt. This underscores the notion that violence and unethical conduct are also attributed to Israel. In essence, the same set of facts can be recounted from diverse viewpoints, influencing the language used.

As demonstrated, when utilizing Artificial Intelligence algorithms to summarize news, these perspectives are interwoven in the resulting texts. Therefore, the first source of bias stems from the newspapers aligning themselves with a particular ideological stance, a factor identified in various studies (Ban et al., 2019; Hjarvard, 2010; Ho et al., 2008). The opinions and reporting style of journalists shaped the summary without giving the script user the ability to precisely choose what to emphasize or omit. This lack of control over the highlighting process is linked to the black box effect, common in the latest machine learning algorithms, where the internal workings of the algorithm remain opaque, as elucidated by Guidotti et al. (2018). Consequently, users are unaware of the specific criteria or biases influencing information selection in the summary. This lack of transparency not only diminishes user agency but also raises concerns about the potential reinforcement of existing biases within the summarization process.

Another significant factor contributing to bias lies not only in the positioning of newspapers but also in the inherent bias inherited from the underlying language model, specifically the DaVinci model's overall training data. Indeed, studies, such as those conducted by Johnson et al. (2022), reveal that ChatGPT is predominantly trained on English data, comprising 93% of its training set. Consequently, when the training data is predominantly Anglophone-oriented, the language model tends to prioritize responses aligning with perspectives commonly found in Anglophone countries, particularly the United States. This bias becomes especially pronounced in the context of Israel and Palestine, where the American perspective, as portrayed in national newspapers, tends to favor Israel. As mentioned earlier, implicit biases are often more insidious than we might acknowledge, with a prevailing belief that AI can aid in reducing biases. However, when these models are implemented across various technologies, the opinions we form may be based on information filtered through a specific discourse. Placing undue reliance on AI algorithms, assuming they are entirely unbiased, can inadvertently result in the absorption of biases. By employing English-trained language models and integrating them into our software, we adopt a specific hierarchy of values that elevates English discourse over others. The paradox lies in these models reproducing a positioned discourse while simultaneously asserting that Artificial Intelligence can be less biased due to its lack of a human perspective.

A second point to note about AI-generated texts is that, due to their limited linguistic competence in terms of pragmatics, as noted by Hu et al. (2022), they frequently connect and compare information that is unrelated in terms of topic. This results in an inability to organize information hierarchically, which can pose significant challenges, especially when dealing with politically sensitive topics and news. Let us reconsider some excerpts from the automatically generated summaries with this observation in mind:

- (6) "Other stories include Taylor Swift fans turning out for a record-breaking concert movie, Julia Louis-Dreyfus on grief, new roles, and the Seinfeld reunion, an annular solar eclipse, and a trial involving Sam Bankman-Fried." (Automatic summary from *The Guardian* homepage, October 13th, 2023)
- (7) "The possibility of human immortality is discussed, as well as the last great mystery of the mind: do you hear a voice in your head or not? The World Bank is launching a campaign to raise funds to fight climate change" (Automatic summary from *El Pais* homepage, October 13th, 2023)
- (8) "Finally, the newspaper covers a variety of topics, from the antisemitic protests in Europe to the upcoming "Suits"

sequel, Renata Lusin's pregnancy, and the wild theories behind Helene Fischer's dildo stunt." (Automatic summary from *Bild* homepage, October 13th, 2023)

- (9) "The page also features several articles that are exclusive to subscribers, such as an interview with Thierry Marx about the potential for total "uberization" of society, a chronicle about Microsoft receiving a "rather salty letter" from the US federal tax service, and a tribune about French teleworking habits." (Automatic summary from *Le Monde* homepage, October 13th, 2023)
- (10) "In France, a teacher was killed in a school in Arras, in the north of the country. The attacker shouted "Allah Akbar" and was arrested. The French government has raised the alert level for terrorist attacks . . . In the Under 21s, Salvatore Riggio of Bari was sent home from the national team after a fight with Matteo Ruggeri, in which Riggio broke Ruggeri's nose with a punch." (Automatic summary from *Il Corriere della Sera* homepage, October 13th, 2023)
- (11) "The emergency level in France has been raised to the highest level. Leger Uten Grenser has reported that the deadline for the evacuation of al-Awda hospital in Gaza has been postponed until Saturday morning. A woman in Norway has been able to reduce her pain after 26 years with the help of her doctor. Shampoo prices vary greatly, but the content is almost the same, according to a professor. A journalist being killed in an Israeli attack on Lebanon." (Automatic summary from *Aftenposten* homepage, October 13th, 2023)

The automatically generated summary by *The Guardian* groups different types of news together, by combining information about Taylor Swift's concert, the new roles of American actress Julia Louis-Dreyfus, the high-profile trial involving Sam Bankman-Fried (the case concerning the son of two Stanford University professors who was involved in a cryptocurrency scandal), and then reports about a recent Hamas attack. All of these topics are presented in close proximity, and they share a similar level of linguistic attention. However, this approach can be problematic. When the software eventually summarizes these various topics, they may be given equal importance, or at the very least, the inclusion of entertainment news in the summary could detract from more important information. A similar issue arises in *El Pais*, where news about longevity enterprises and studies on artificial intelligence for brain activity detection are equated with the World Bank launching a campaign to combat climate change. In this case, the language model is not comparing gossip to

political news, but rather, it is summarizing information in a way that becomes syntactically ambiguous. After a question mark, there is a completely different news story. As language models are not fully capable of understanding the pragmatic context, this deficiency manifests in the syntax, with sentences listing unrelated pieces of information. Even more remarkable is one of the examples from the *Bild*, where, at the conclusion of the summary, we find the alarming juxtaposition of rising antisemitic protests in Europe with discussions about the next season of a TV series or even speculations about a famous Germany singer's sexuality. In other words, it appears that there is no hierarchy in assessing the sensitive value of information. Again, in the summary from *Le Monde*, the war between Israel and Hamas receives less space than the four lines dedicated to advertising a subscription to *Le Monde*, and consequently, the amount of political information about arguably the most important news in international politics in this summary is quite scarce. In the case of *Il Corriere della Sera*, soccer news has been allocated the same linguistic space as the report regarding a terror attack in France. Probably the most striking example of this lack of value understanding comes from the *Afterposten*, where the prices of shampoo, a murder in Lebanon, and the evacuation of a hospital in Gaza are given the same level of linguistic space and a comparable number of tokens.

The lack of pragmatic competence eventually led us to a discussion revolving around the debate on the actual intelligence, in terms of a proper understanding, of these models. While some scholars highlight the parallels between large language models and human capacities, emphasizing their supposed emotional intelligence (Wang et al., 2023) or general understanding abilities (Bubeck et al., 2023), others offer different perspectives on the same technology and underscore its limitations and lack of proper contextual understanding (Davis & Marcus, 2015; Floridi, 2023). Interestingly, a study by LeDoux et al. (2023) leans towards hardware-based theories for a specific reason, arguing that biology plays a crucial role. Considering that all known conscious beings obtain energy by metabolizing organic molecules, work to maintain a stable internal environment, and process information through neural networks that utilize both chemical and electrical signals, scientists suggest that if these characteristics are shared among all conscious entities, it is plausible to hypothesize that one or more of these features might be essential for consciousness. For the purposes of our paper, the crucial point is that these models are incapable of assessing the value of the information they generate and prioritizing it, despite occasional claims to the contrary. As sophisticated "stochastic parrots" (p. 616) merely replicating data, as argued by Bender et al. (2021), they ultimately need guidance during the training process and the deployment of the models, especially in the conceptual organization of the data.

For the concluding section of this paper, we will explore the comprehensive summary generated by the Python pipeline, beginning with the following examples:

- (12) The newspapers reported on the escalating conflict between Israel and Hamas, which has caused thousands of Palestinians to flee northern Gaza in fear.
- (13) The US is attempting to broker a way out of Gaza for foreigners and set up Palestinian “safe zones.”
- (14) The Institute of Molecular Medicine Gulbenkian, the government's plan to provide direct support to families, the freedom of Sara Correia, the Leffest event, the Poker Face series, and the photography exhibition in Tires.

What we can discern is that the verb ‘to flee’ has been eventually reproduced by the language model, as it appeared twice in the seven summaries provided, with the consequential linguistic perspective being inherited. The usage of this verb implies that the people from Gaza were always able to escape, which was not always the case. This could be seen as a prime example of political bias, which, while not intentional, remains highly significant. Another instance of this bias is the representation of the United States as assisting Gaza and helping establish Palestinian safe zones, exhibited by the depiction of the US as attempting to ‘broker a way out of Gaza’ and ‘set up Palestinian ‘safe zones’, while some sources place great responsibility and geopolitical interests on U.S. actions (Simon & Stevenson, 2023). Additionally, there is an issue with poor syntax stemming from the language model's attempt to condense summaries into a fixed length, with sentences lacking a verb, rendering them nonsensical. For example, the sentence ‘the Institute of Molecular Medicine Gulbenkian’ is presented as part of a linguistic comparison when it should be a standalone news item. The absence of a verb in this sentence reduces it to a mere subject without any action.

Also, as the preceding summaries frequently intertwine news and information from entirely different contexts within a single sentence, the overall summary exhibits a similar pattern. Gossip about singer Sarah Correia, news regarding a photography exhibition, and information about the Biden administration's support for Israel are all bundled together as if they share equal importance.

5. Conclusion

In conclusion, while AI-generated content has significant potential to boost productivity and efficiency, it also presents a number of complex challenges that must be addressed. To better understand the potential pitfalls of using AI and large language models (LLMs) for drafting journalistic texts, we developed

a pipeline to summarize the homepage of seven different newspapers in various languages, which then provided us with an overall general summary. This approach allowed us to assess the emergence of inaccuracies and biases in AI-generated texts.

To support readers in our analysis and provide context for our findings, we included relevant information to help them better understand the implications. Given this goal, we began by introducing the concept of large language models (LLMs) and delving into their functioning. We first explored the potential for generating text with these models and the challenges involved in identifying AI-generated content. Research indicated that, despite the development of software capable of such identification, the process of creating linguistically convincing text through AI is significantly more efficient than detecting AI-generated text. Consequently, adapting to a world where AI-generated texts are increasingly prevalent has become imperative.

As AI-generated content saturates journalism, it introduces numerous challenges. One of these challenges is the presence of biases, which can have substantial political implications. Additionally, Language Models are often insufficient to evaluate the value of information within various pragmatic contexts, making it difficult to compare information from different domains and prioritize information reliably. There are two primary issues to explore further: poor syntax due to fixed text length, political bias, and a lack of context and hierarchical understanding. These issues are worth further investigation, both in relation to our software and potentially within the subfield of Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA) applied to technological discourse and Language Modeling.

In summary, it is imperative to approach these technologies with a critical perspective. We should avoid embracing an overly optimistic view that portrays artificial intelligence as the ultimate solution for every problem in the world. Simultaneously, we should not outright reject these systems and should recognize their ability to perform significant tasks. As students, researchers, and professors, our responsibility is to scrutinize these issues and engage in discussions using the critical tools provided by the humanities.

Notes

1. In data science, a classifier is a machine learning algorithm used to assign a specific label to a data input. For instance, a text classifier might categorize a sentence as belonging to one of several categories, such as "sports," "politics," or "entertainment."
2. "Prompt" refers to a specific set of words, phrases, or instructions given to a software to initiate or guide their language production, typically in the

context of language modeling. A 'prompt' serves as input or stimulus for generating a linguistic response.

3. A pipeline is a series of data processing stages or operations connected in sequence, where the output of one stage serves as the input to the next. It is a term commonly used in the context of data processing, data analysis, or software development workflows.
4. Specifically, the prompt was as follows: "You are a journalist tasked with preparing a daily report. Read the first page of the newspaper, [...] translate the news into English, and provide me with a summary." In brackets, the model was fed the homepage of the scraped newspaper.

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